

Modeling of Impact Damage and Compression After Impact of Laminated Composite Aerospace Structures

ICCM22 – Melbourne, Australia, August 2019

Anthony M. Waas

*Richard A Auhl Department Chair
Aerospace Engineering
University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, USA*

Presented by

Paul Davidson

*Assistant Research Scientist, Aerospace Engineering,
University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, USA*

Acknowledgments:

1. *ICCM22 Committee for inviting me*
2. *The Boeing Company, Seattle and MHI-Japan for sponsoring this study*
3. *Shiyao Lin and Solver Thorsson for much of the work in the presentation*

Contents

1. Introduction and Motivation
 2. Experimental Investigation
 3. Numerical Investigation
 4. Conclusion and Discussion
-

1. Introduction and Motivation

- LVI induces extensive internal damage with minimal external indicators.
- Damage modes: **fiber breakage**, **matrix cracking** and **delamination**.
- Significant knock down for compressive strength.
- LVI tests are expensive.
- Computational models are mostly based on finite element method (FEM).

1. Introduction and Motivation (Cont.)

- Damage modes are almost always interacting with each other.
- Many progressive damage analysis models have been proposed.
- The quasi-isotropic $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ stacking sequence has a featured “**rotating fan**” damage pattern. Which is mainly due to the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination.
- The quasi-isotropic stacking sequence is one of the best examples for LVI studies, because:
 - i. It is widely used.
 - ii. The “**rotating fan**” reveals the mechanism of damage mode interaction.
 - iii. It can be used as a **benchmark** to examine LVI predictive models.

Damage modes interaction

Contents

1. Introduction and Motivation
 2. Experimental Investigation
 3. Numerical Investigation
 4. Conclusions and Discussions
-

2. Experimental Investigation

- Stacking sequences: **[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}** (T800S/3900-2B: interface toughened) and several non-traditional (NTL) lay-ups.
- Impactor mass: 7.5Kg. Impact energies: **25J** (recommended by ASTM D7136).
- Instron CEAST Dynatup 9350 drop tower system.
- Two Photron SA-X high-speed cameras and Aramis for **3D DIC**
- Ultrasound **C-scanning** and X-ray **micro-CT** (with dye penetrant) for NDIs.

Impact fixture

Test setup

- Highly repetitive test results.
- No large oscillations in load on the curves are seen, indicating that there is no severe damage (BVID).

2. Experimental Investigation: 3D DIC

Center Displacement history

Section Displacement history

- The bottom (unimpacted) out-of-plane displacement field is **smooth**, meaning no significant damage (fiber rupture) on the bottom surface.

Displacement field history

Top and bottom surface center disp. history

- Residual displacement** of a small finite value is captured.
- The bottom center displacement deviates from the top center displacement after 0.8 ms, which is due to the **highly localized deformation** on the top (impacted) surface.

2. Experimental Investigation: Non-destructive investigations (NDIs)

- The time-of-flight (TOF) data was used to indicate damage.
- Fiber kinking on the topmost 45° ply and delamination are clearly observed. The delamination footprints are almost circular, due to the stacking sequence being quasi-isotropic.

2. Experimental Investigation: Non-destructive investigations (NDIs)

40
mm

- Micro-CT scanning is performed with dye penetrant containing Zinc Iodide.
- The “**rotating fan**” pattern of delamination is clearly observed in the face-on slices.
- **Damage-free cone** is seen in the edge-on slices.

2. Experimental Investigation: NDIs Cont.

Damage Mechanisms

- Matrix splitting exists with a finite crack spacing.
- Multiple matrix splitting serves as initiation for the delamination.

2. Summary of the Experimental Investigation

- The load-time, load-displacement curves are highly repetitive and smooth, indicating no significant damage (under BVID).
- The impact damage footprint is almost **circular**.
- Features such as the “**rotating fan**” **delamination pattern** and the **damage-free cone** are observed from the micro-CT scanning.
- **Damage interaction mechanisms** are illustrated by micro-CT scanning.

Take-aways from Prior work.....

(4) Olsson et al "Modelling of impact damage zones in composite laminates for strength after impact." Aeronautical Journal, 116 (1186): 1349-1365, 2012

- It has been shown that the use of simplified damage patterns are not desired for predicting CSAI
 - Use of simplified delamination patterns
 - Estimated damage areas, circular or elliptical, with non-physical over all constituents degradation
- Correct Approach: Predict the impacted laminates damage state sufficiently accurately which will result in the CSAI to be predicted correctly

a) 0°/45° ply and interface damage

b) 0°/90° ply and interface damage

≠ Experimental CAI

Contents

1. Introduction and Motivation
 2. Experimental Investigation
 3. Numerical Investigation
 4. Conclusions and Discussions
-

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Model

- Intra-ply Model: Enhanced Schapery Theory (EST) (VUMAT)**

Schapery Theory – Pre-peak non-linearity

- Captures the pre-peak matrix dominated non-linearity due to microscopic damage.

Crack Band– Post-peak strain softening

- Captures the post-peak strain softening due to macroscopic cracks
 - Fiber rupture/kinking
 - Matrix macroscopic cracking

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Model

- Intra-ply Model: Shear Nonlinearity**

$\pm 45^\circ$ in-plane tensile testing

Dissipated energy vs. shear strain

Dissipated energy (the Schapery function)

- Inter-ply Model: Cohesive Contact (in-built in Abaqus)**

- General contact when the two adjacent surfaces are contacting.
- Following cohesive traction-separation law when the two adjacent surfaces are separating.
- Compared to methods using cohesive element, the model with cohesive contact is numerically stable, and the pre-processing is more convenient.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Model

- **Modeling Strategy**

- User-defined material (EST) for intraply damage and Abaqus cohesive contact for interply delamination.
- A global-local mesh strategy is used: $0.6 \times 0.6 \text{ mm}^2$ (local fine mesh) and $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^2$ (global coarse mesh)
- Contact: Frictional coefficient=0.3. Pre-peak penalty stiffness= $1 \text{e}5 \text{ N/mm}$
- 600,000 elements, analyzed time 8 ms, 64 CPUs, runtime ~20hrs.

3. Numerical Investigation: Numerical Results-Curves

Critical parameters

	Test result	Numerical result	Error
Max impact load (N)	10571.7	10857.7	2.6%
Time at the max load (ms)	2.57	2.64	2.6%
Impact duration (ms)	5.51	5.64	2.8%
Max impactor displacement (mm)	4.46	4.58	2.6%

Fiber debris stopping matrix cracking from fully closing
(Bouvet, 2012)

- The predicted curves agree very well with the test curves. The critical parameters are all predicted **within 3% error**.
- From the displacement-load curve, the residual displacement is not predicted, because the residual strain effect (caused by fiber debris, fiber entanglement, friction between delaminated plies) is yet in the damage model.

3. Numerical Investigation: Numerical Results-Displacements

Bottom surface disp. Field (3D DIC)

Bottom surface disp. field (EST)

Top and bottom surface center disp. history

- Tested and predicted displacement fields are very similar.
- The center displacement history curves are almost identical. On both top and bottom surfaces, the **predicted ones bounces back faster than the DIC captured results.**
- The **local high curvatures** of the sectional displacement are captured by both DIC and EST prediction.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

Damage footprint

Compared with C-scanning, the predicted delamination **footprint's shape and size are agreeable.**

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

- Before (i), the load-time curve is smooth. The damage area growth rate is slow.
- From (ii) to (v), the damage area growth rate becomes higher. Oscillations are seen in the load-time curve.
- After (v), which correspond to the peak load, damage stops growing.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

- The "rotating fan" pattern of delamination has been captured, although predictions on the top few interfaces, can be improved (overpredicted)
- The **damage-free cone** in the center has been predicted.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

Matrix Cracking

- In ply 6 to ply 24, the **matrix cracking is along the fiber direction**.
- Compared with the micro-CT scanning, the matrix cracking predicted is not sharp. In crack band, the crack separation is smeared over a characteristic width.
- The area associated with matrix cracking is sufficiently resolved.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

Fiber Kinking

- Only the topmost five plies have fiber kinking damage.
- In ply 1, 2, 4 and 5, fiber kinking is predicted correctly as being perpendicular to the fiber direction.
- Fiber kinking damage concentrates to bands spanning over only the width of one element.
- Due to highly curved local deformation near the top surface, it is not possible to obtain ply-by-ply fiber kinking information from the micro-CT, but some resemblance is found.

3. Numerical Investigation: Damage Prediction

Damage Mode Interaction

Fiber kinking-Delamination Interaction

Matrix cracking-Delamination Interaction

- Interaction between fiber kinking and delamination is captured.
- Interaction between matrix splitting and delamination is captured.
- No explicit interaction mechanism is included in the user subroutine.
- A fiber-aligned mesh is not used.

CAI FE Model: CAI Results for Quasi and NTL's

- CAI predictions for the TL impacts were slightly under-predicted – the reason?
 - The top five interface delamination areas are overpredicted.
- NTL coupons showed excellent agreement
 - 6 laminates were within 7.2% of the experimental average as well as being within or close to the experimental bound
 - Overall results were within 14.4% of the experimental average

(b) 100% BVID

(d) NTL-1

(f) NTL-6

Face-on Impact & CAI Model: CAI in Detail for the TL model

Typical Experimental Failure

Contents

1. Introduction and Motivation
 2. Experimental Investigation
 3. Numerical Investigation
 4. Conclusions and Discussion
-

4. Conclusions and Discussion

- The prediction of the impacted state in terms of load-time and load-displacement responses is of high quality. The errors of the critical parameters are all within **3%**.
- The internal damage is well predicted, in terms of the overall damage footprint and detailed **ply-by-ply and interface-by-interface damage**.
- The features including the “**rotating fan**” **delamination** pattern and the **damage-free cone** are well predicted, which have hardly been modeled or reported in previous work.
- **The correct reproduction of the damage mode interaction is the key reason for such a good detailed damage prediction.** However, challenges remain – the balance between high fidelity and computational efficiency!

Challenges in modeling

- *Models* that capture different failure mechanisms (energy dissipation) in the presence of *multiple failure modes*
- Methods that can correctly capture *failure mode interactions*
- Methods that can simulate the effects of different responses in, for example, tension and compression without recourse to extensive detail that can render the *prediction computationally prohibitive*

On-going work: Carrera, Kaleel and Waas – use of CUF for damage and failure analysis of composite structures

Thank You! Questions?
